

Laudate Deum: An Apostolic Exhortation on Climate Change

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Abstract

On 4th October 2023, Holy Father Pope Francis published an apostolic exhortation *Laudate Deum*, a follow-up document to the well-acclaimed encyclical *Laudato Si'*. A wide range of issues such as pollution, climate change, fresh drinking water, loss of biodiversity, decline in the quality of life, breakdown of society, globalization etc., find their place in this papal document. Climate change is a global problem with serious implications: environmental, social, economic, political and for the distribution of goods. It represents one of the principal challenges facing humanity in our day. Today, more than ever before, a fresh understanding that people and the planet are part of one interdependent and interconnected earth community. Our very vocation as human beings is to protect, preserve and conserve the God-given resources in our common home. Hence this article focuses on Pope Francis' clarion call to deal with climate change today.

Introduction

After the ground-breaking encyclical *Laudato Si'* which was published eight years ago, as a sequel to it Pope Francis has brought out another apostolic exhortation *Laudate Deum* on 4th October 2023. In the context of global climate change, this apostolic exhortation is very timely. It is for the first time a church document is entirely dealing with climate change. In this article, an attempt is made to look into the impact of climate change as observed by Pope Francis.

1. The Global Impact of Climate Change

The study of climate change has emerged in the last three decades as one of the most vexed and contentious areas of contemporary scientific endeavour

(Stephen Bede Scharper, 30). According to Stephen Bede Scharper, “From the muzzling of environmental scientists and the closing of ecological research centers in Canada to the censorship of leading climate change researchers in the United States, such as NASA climate scientist James Hansen, politics has tintured, tethered, and at times eclipsed scientific data on one of the most crucial issues of our times” (Stephen Bede Scharper, 30). In the words of Naomi Klein, “Climate change isn’t an ‘issue’ to add to the list of things to worry about, next to health care and taxes. It is a civilizational wake-up call” (Naomi Klein). According to Walter Leal Filho, “Climate change as a whole, and global warming in particular, are known to have a negative impact on biodiversity in three main ways. Firstly, increases in temperatures are known to be detrimental to a number of organisms, especially those in sensitive habitats such as coral reefs and rainforests. Secondly, the pressures posed by a changing climate may lead to sets of responses in areas as varied as phenology, range and physiology of living organisms, often leading to changes in life cycles..losses in productivity, or even death...Thirdly, the impacts of climate change on biodiversity are estimated to be felt in the short term in respect of some species and ecosystems, but also in the medium and long term in many biomes. Indeed, if left unattended, some of these impacts may be irreversible” (Walter Leal Filho).In *Laudate Deum*, Pope Francis addresses his concern: “The world in which we live is collapsing and may be nearing the breaking point. In addition to this possibility, it is indubitable that the impact of climate change will increasingly prejudice the lives and families of many persons. We will feel its effects in the areas of healthcare, sources of employment, access to resources, housing, forced migrations, etc.” (*Laudate Deum*, 2). He further writes:

This is a global social issue and one intimately related to the dignity of human life. The Bishops of the United States have expressed very well this social meaning of our concern about climate change, which goes beyond a merely ecological approach, because “our care for one another and our care for the earth are intimately bound together. Climate change is one of the principal challenges facing society and the global community. The effects of climate change are borne by the most vulnerable people, whether at home or around the world (*Laudate Deum*, 3).

Thus we know climate change is due to factors such as temperature, atmospheric carbon dioxide, and cloud cover etc have a direct impact on the growth of plants and trees. As a result climate change is affecting natural

habitats and ecosystems via altering environmental factors. There are even subtle adjustments which can have a great impact on the species living within an ecosystem (Sarah Moore). The effect of climate change can be observed at various levels. In the water bodies especially in the ocean, water temperatures are rising and becoming more acidic. On land, temperatures are rising as well, and soil health and freshwater quality are declining. Consequently, there is an endangering of entire ecosystems (UCAR).

Since temperatures continue to rise, many species are not able to thrive in places where they once lived. Today scientists estimate that 8% of current animal species are at risk of extinction due to climate change alone. Near the equator, a region with Earth's highest biodiversity, many species are not able to adapt to rising temperatures. It is also estimated that by 2070 nearly 20% of tropical plant species will be unable to germinate because of temperatures beyond their upper limit (UCAR). It is said that "the bushfire that burned over 25 million acres in Australia during 2019-2020, which started due to a lightning strike following an especially hot, dry spell, killed an estimated one billion animals. Many of the animals that died in these fires are found only in Australia, which raises concern about the future of these unique ecosystems" (UCAR).

2. The Climate Change and Human Ecology

Human ecology is all about the study of the relationships between people and their environment. It evolves on the analysis and deep understanding of mechanisms of biology, geography, environmental and natural sciences, sociology, economics, and other human sciences, next to applied sciences as medicine and engineering. It "not only integrates in its approach the (environmental, social, and economic) dimensions of sustainable development but equally pays attention to the cultural, psychological, and welfare dimensions of the equation" (An Think Nguyen, 4). Human ecology is also concerned about the reciprocal relationships between the biophysical and the socio-economic environment in its widest context. According to the human ecologist, the environment is perceived as an ecosystem which is a wide concept both when it comes to its nature and its size. In an ecosystem everything is in a specified physical area – air, water, and soil – which interacts with the biological organisms and physical structures: it is about the organisms in a lake which not only depend on each other but are also influenced by the water they swim in, the quality of the water bottom, and the air above the water surface. Human ecology thus extends the ecosystem

concept to areas in which humans are an important factor: a city, a farm, a tourism resort, and cultural assets etc.(An Think Nguyen, 4).

Climate change contributes to the migration of people to safer places. They are called environmental refugees who are displaced persons crossing borders due to climate change effects. In recent times environmental refugees attracted the attention of researchers. The relationship between climate change and migration is complex and varies over time. Drought, desertification, and land degradation leading to food and water shortage are considered driving forces of local displacement as a result of the decline in agricultural yields. Extreme weather events are the main reason for affected people to leave their homes and move toward safer areas. The effects of climate change on migration affect people in the developing countries of Africa and Asia more and make them moving faster. That is why migration is considered a strategy to climate change adaptation (An Think Nguyen, 9-10).

Pope Francis underlines that the climate is a common good, belonging to all and meant for all. The scientific community attests to the fact that we are presently witnessing a disturbing warming of the climatic system. Already in *Laudato Si'* the Pope wrote:

In recent decades this warming has been accompanied by a constant rise in the sea level and, it would appear, by an increase of extreme weather events, even if a scientifically determinable cause cannot be assigned to each particular phenomenon. Humanity is called to recognize the need for changes of lifestyle, production and consumption, to combat this warming or at least the human causes which produce or aggravate it. There are indeed other factors (such as volcanic activity, variations in the earth's orbit and axis, and the solar cycle), yet several scientific studies indicate that most global warming in recent decades is due to the great concentration of greenhouse gases (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides and others) released mainly as a result of human activity. As these gases build up in the atmosphere, they hamper the escape of heat produced by sunlight at the earth's surface. The problem is aggravated by a model of development based on the intensive use of fossil fuels, which is at the heart of the worldwide energy system. Another determining factor has been an increase in changed uses of the soil, principally deforestation for agricultural purposes (*Laudato Si'*,23).

Pope Francis further states:

Warming has effects on the carbon cycle. It creates a vicious circle which aggravates the situation even more, affecting the availability of essential resources like drinking water, energy and agricultural production in warmer regions, and leading to the extinction of part of the planet's biodiversity. The melting in the polar ice caps and in high altitude plains can lead to the dangerous release of methane gas, while the decomposition of frozen organic material can further increase the emission of carbon dioxide. Things are made worse by the loss of tropical forests which would otherwise help to mitigate climate change. Carbon dioxide pollution increases the acidification of the oceans and compromises the marine food chain (*Laudato Si*,24).

“If present trends continue,” the Pope says, “this century may well witness extraordinary climate change and an unprecedented destruction of ecosystems, with serious consequences for all of us” (*Laudato Si*,24). The global challenge of climate change is well articulated in *Laudato Si*'. Pope Francis is very sensitive to the problems of the poor and the migrants who are mostly affected by the consequences of climate change.

Climate change is a global problem with grave implications: environmental, social, economic, political and for the distribution of goods. It represents one of the principal challenges facing humanity in our day. Its worst impact will probably be felt by developing countries in the coming decades. Many of the poor live in areas particularly affected by phenomena related to warming, and their means of subsistence are largely dependent on natural reserves and ecosystemic services such as agriculture, fishing and forestry. They have no other financial activities or resources which can enable them to adapt to climate change or to face natural disasters, and their access to social services and protection is very limited. For example, changes in climate, to which animals and plants cannot adapt, lead them to migrate; this in turn affects the livelihood of the poor, who are then forced to leave their homes, with great uncertainty for their future and that of their children. There has been a tragic rise in the number of migrants seeking to flee from the growing poverty caused by environmental degradation. They are not recognized by international conventions as refugees; they bear the loss of the lives they have left behind, without enjoying any legal protection whatsoever. Sadly, there is widespread indifference to such suffering, which is even now taking place throughout our world. Our lack of response to these tragedies involving our brothers and sisters points to the loss of that sense of

responsibility for our fellow men and women up on which all civil society is founded (*Laudato Si*,25).

Four years after the publication of *Laudato Si'*, in his address to the finance ministers of various nations on 27th May 2019, Pope Francis emphasized that we need to resolve to work together for the following ends (Pope Francis, Climate Change):

- i. to value what is important, not what is superfluous;
- ii. to correct our national accounts and our business accounts, so as to stop engaging in activities that are destroying our planet;
- iii. to put an end to global dependency on fossil fuels;
- iv. to open a new chapter of clean and safe energy, that utilizes, for example, renewable resources such as wind, sun and water;
- v. above all, to act prudently and responsibly in our economies to actually meet human needs, promote human dignity, help the poor and be set free of the idolatry of money that creates so much suffering.

Thus Pope Francis is a person totally committed to the global concern of climate change and its impact on the world at large. Time and again the Pope emphasizes the interconnectedness of humans with nature. As he says:

It cannot be emphasized enough how everything is interconnected. Time and space are not independent of one another, and not even atoms or subatomic particles can be considered in isolation. Just as the different aspects of the planet— physical, chemical and biological—are interrelated, so too living species are part of a network which we will never fully explore and understand. A good part of our genetic code is shared by many living beings. It follows that the fragmentation of knowledge and the isolation of bits of information can actually become a form of ignorance unless they are integrated into a broader vision of reality (*Laudato Si*,67).

3. The Spiritual Motivations

After having presented the impact of climate change at the global level the Pope insists on the need of a spiritual reawakening and promoting and fostering the transformative effect of faith. As he writes:

I cannot fail in this regard to remind the Catholic faithful of the motivations born of their faith. I encourage my brothers and sisters of other religions to do the same since we know that authentic faith not only gives strength to the human heart but also transforms life,

transfigures our goals and sheds light on our relationship to others and with creation as a whole (*Laudate Deum*, 61).

He also highlights the theological bases of environmental care, which on the part of the believer is a call for recognition and admiration of Creation. In this regard, Jesus is the model par excellence. Pope Francis observes that Jesus “was able to invite others to be attentive to the beauty that there is in the world because he himself was in constant touch with nature, lending it an attraction full of fondness and wonder. As he made his way throughout the land, he often stopped to contemplate the beauty sown by his Father, and invited his disciples to perceive a divine message in things” (*Laudate Deum*, 64).

Pope invites us on a “pilgrimage of reconciliation.” As he writes:

I ask everyone to accompany this pilgrimage of reconciliation with the world that is our home and to help make it more beautiful, because that commitment has to do with our personal dignity and highest values. At the same time, I cannot deny that it is necessary to be honest and recognize that the most effective solutions will not come from individual efforts alone, but above all from major political decisions on the national and international level (*Laudate Deum*, 69).

Finally, the Pope appeals that every household should make earnest efforts to reduce pollution and waste, and to consume with prudence, and thus creating a new culture. He says, “The mere fact that personal, family and community habits are changing is contributing to greater concern about the unfulfilled responsibilities of the political sectors and indignation at the lack of interest shown by the powerful. Let us realize, then, that even though this does not immediately produce a notable effect from the quantitative standpoint, we are helping to bring about large processes of transformation rising from deep within society” (*Laudate Deum*, 71).

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